

Estimation of the prevalence of neuronal synuclein disease in the United States

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Abstract

The biological definition of neuronal synucleinopathies, termed Neuronal Synuclein Disease (NSD), raises the question of how many individuals are likely to belong to this group. In this commentary we have reviewed the literature in order to estimate how many people in the USA who are diagnosed with Parkinson's disease (PD), Dementia with Lewy Bodies (DLB), and Alzheimer's disease (AD) are likely to be positive for in the alpha-synuclein seed amplification assay (SAA), or a related marker of neuronal alpha-synuclein aggregation, and thereby fulfill the key NSD diagnostic criterion. Furthermore, we have estimated how many people who currently are in the prodromal stages of Parkinson's disease and DLB who are likely to be positive for alpha-synuclein aggregates. Finally, we discuss how many asymptomatic individuals aged 40 years and above in the USA are likely to exhibit positive biomarkers of alpha-synuclein. Our conclusions are that there are around 4-5 million people diagnosed with PD, DLB or AD who fall into the NSD category. In addition, we estimate that around 1 million people who exhibit prodromal signs and symptoms of PD and DLB are positive for alpha-synuclein aggregates. In addition to these people who exhibit signs of neurodegenerative disease, we estimate that there are around 13 million Americans over the age of 40 who would test positive for alpha-synuclein aggregates. We discuss our estimates in the context of the possibility that emerging drugs targeting alpha-synuclein aggregates might be helpful in treating a larger group of people exhibiting signs of synucleinopathy than those diagnosed with PD and DLB today, and that future treatments might be more effective if one can interfere earlier in the disease process. Finally, we speculate whether the development of additional biomarkers to accurately identify those who are most likely to develop symptoms of neurodegeneration, means that secondary prevention of synucleinopathies might be possible in the future.

The alpha-synuclein seed amplification assay and neuronal synuclein disease

A new position paper in *Lancet Neurology* proposes a biological definition of neuronal synucleinopathies new integrated staging system for Neuronal Synuclein Disease (NSD-ISS) ¹. This staging system is a research framework rooted in availability of a biomarker of a-syn pathology, including the recently published validation of the alpha-synuclein seed amplification assay (SAA) in 1,123 participants from the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) cohort, demonstrating that, when the assay is applied to cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) samples, it accurately differentiates idiopathic Parkinson's disease (PD) from healthy controls ². These results support the high sensitivity and specificity for neuronal alpha synucleinopathies noted by numerous studies using different versions of SAAs in CSF samples in independent cohorts, summarized by two large systematic reviews and meta-analyses ^{3,4}. Notably, the PPMI study also revealed that 86% of participants with signs of *prodromal* PD (e.g. REM sleep behavior disorder or hyposmia) associated with dopaminergic dysfunction were SAA positive ². In addition, several studies began to apply the SAA to other biomatrices such as blood, skin, saliva and olfactory mucosa ⁵⁻¹³. While further validation of the assays in these biomatrices and confirmation in additional and larger cohorts are needed, probably the SAA will be applicable to such readily available biomatrices and therefore a diagnosis of Neuronal Synuclein Disease (NSD) is likely to be made relatively simply and at a low cost in the future. NSD departs from traditional diagnosis of PD and DLB based on the clinical criteria to disease defined by biology that can be diagnosed even in absence of any signs and symptoms. In NSD-ISS Stage 1A, people are only positive on the SAA test without evidence of dopaminergic dysfunction and do not present with any motor or cognitive symptoms associated with PD and Dementia with Lewy bodies (DLB) ¹ (see Table 1). In stage 1B, there is the addition of evidence of dopaminergic dysfunction (e.g. based on any validated biomarker, currently DAT brain imaging) but still no relevant signs or symptoms. Thus, the NSD-ISS states that people who are in Stage 1 have the disease even though they are asymptomatic, and will go on to develop the clinical features of either PD or DLB. Thus, people who are currently diagnosed as PD or DLB have the same disease that can manifest with a spectrum of clinical syndromes, including predominantly motor and cognitive phenotypes. Notably,

the ultrastructure of alpha-synuclein aggregates, as defined by analysis using cryo-electron microscopy ¹⁴, are very similar in PD and DLB. These aggregates differ in structure from those in Multiple System Atrophy (MSA), where the alpha-synuclein aggregates are primarily found in oligodendroglia. Moreover, for CSF samples obtained from people with PD and DLB the alpha-synuclein aggregates in the SAA exhibit similar biophysical properties, but differ to those seen when the SAA is performed with samples from MSA patients ¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Because the synucleinopathy in MSA is mostly glial ¹⁸, these patients are not included under the umbrella of NSD. Notably, alpha-synucleinopathy is primarily neuronal in both PD and DLB and there are several similarities between the neuropathologies of DLB and advanced PD ¹⁸, particularly at stages when significant dementia is apparent, and both conditions are also frequently (in 50-90% of cases) associated with neuropathologies characteristic of AD ^{19,20,21}. The genetic risk landscapes of DLB and PD also display similarities ²². Taken together, these observations underscore that underlying disease mechanisms overlap significantly between PD and DLB, though the reason for the differences in the clinical features, particularly in the early symptomatic stages remain to be defined. Indeed, it has long been suggested that PD and DLB should be viewed as one disease entity, albeit with differing clinical courses ²³. This idea has gained additional traction recently ²⁴ due to the emergence of the SAA for alpha-synuclein and the publication of the NSD-ISS ^{1,2,25}. One of the most fundamental consequences of adopting the NSD-ISS framework is that those who today are clinically diagnosed with PD and DLB will fall into the same diagnostic category. Moreover, the adoption of the NSD diagnostic criteria, focusing on biomarker profile rather than clinical features at the time of diagnosis, has many ramifications for research (e.g. defining the underpinnings of heterogeneity between patients), clinical trial design (e.g. using a positive SAA test as an inclusion criterion for treatments targeting aggregated alpha-synuclein), and potentially also for future clinical practice (e.g. earlier and more accurate diagnosis, and also allowing for an earlier start of future molecularly guided treatments).

Neuronal synuclein disease generates new questions

The emergence of the NSD concept raises several important questions about how many people will fulfill the diagnostic criteria for NSD. *First*, how many people presenting primarily with either motor or cognitive deficits will be diagnosed as having NSD in the future? *Second*, how many people who exhibit no symptoms or overt signs of neurological disease will be SAA positive and could be considered to be on the definite path to developing clinical symptoms? The sizes of these populations are essential because future treatments targeting alpha-synuclein aggregates might be efficacious on the converging pathobiology and thus obtain regulatory approval for NSD (assuming both motor and cognitive endpoints are included in pivotal trials), as opposed to only for PD or DLB. *Third*, a discussion can be started regarding if, and when, it would be appropriate to perform secondary prevention for neurological deficits due to Lewy pathology. A nuanced discussion of secondary prevention in NSD is crucial, because, with our current understanding, the majority of asymptomatic people who test SAA positive are unlikely to develop neurological deficits during their lifetime even in the absence of a treatment.

How many people in the USA exhibit alpha-synuclein aggregates?

Parkinson's disease and Dementia with Lewy Bodies

In this brief commentary, we have chosen to focus on estimating the number of people who could be diagnosed with NSD if the SAA test was used widely in the USA. Today, it can be approximated that the number of people affected by PD is around 1,000,000 in the USA²⁶, a number that can be predicted to double by 2040^{27,28} (Fig. 1A). The recent study validating the SAA in the PPMI cohort suggests that over 90% of those with a PD diagnosis are SAA positive², which is supported by meta-analyses of the literature^{3,4}, resulting in at least 900,000 individuals with NSD (Fig. 1B). Interestingly, the number of people diagnosed with DLB is estimated to be slightly higher, i.e. 1,400,000²⁹ (Fig. 1A). The proportion of those diagnosed with DLB who are SAA positive varies greatly in the literature, probably as a result of differences in traditions when it comes to accurately distinguishing DLB from other common forms of dementia (e.g. Alzheimer's disease [AD] and vascular dementia). The majority of studies state that 70-90% CSF samples from DLB cases are SAA positive^{7, 20, 30-34}) which means

that one can estimate (taking 80% as an approximation) around 1,100,000 people with the clinical diagnosis of DLB exhibit (Fig. 1B). Thus, one can assume that around 2 million people (900,000 PD + 1,100,000 DLB) with motor and/or cognitive impairments who are diagnosed with PD and DLB in the USA today would test positive for SAA and would be classified as having NSD (Fig. 1B).

However, these numbers do not include people who are SAA positive and on a possible path towards developing PD or DLB, but who have not yet developed any clinical symptoms or deficits, i.e. those in stage 1 of the NSD-ISS (Table 1)²⁵. Accurately estimating how many people in the USA today would fall into NSD-ISS stage 1 is challenging and will require systematic population-based study that will be possible once the biomarkers can be assessed in blood or other readily accessible matrices. NSD stage 2, defined by presence of a-syn pathology and clinical prodrome, which includes features such as REM sleep behavior disorder, hyposmia, constipation, anxiety, can be estimated to be around 5-15 years long for PD and DLB^{35,36}. During that phase, a SAA test would be positive with only more subtle clinical signs/symptoms (without functional impairments, i.e. in accordance with the definition of NSD stage 2) that would not qualify for a diagnosis of PD or DLB today, e.g. hyposmia, sleep disorder, mild cognitive deficits, constipation, anxiety etc. The average lifespan of PD and DLB patients is around 10-20 years after diagnosis, depending on the age at onset of symptoms³⁷. Thus, a 'back of the envelope' calculation would suggest that those in Stage 2 of the NSD-ISS typically lasts 5-15 years (only slightly shorter than the duration of the manifest disease itself), and the majority are SAA positive, would represent at least approximately an additional 50% of the number of people who already have a diagnosis of PD or DLB today, i.e. around 1,000,000 (Fig. 1C). Even with this conservative estimate, it would bring the total number up with NSD who exhibit neurological symptoms or signs from around 2 million (PD +DLB) to 3 million (the third million represented by the dark orange circle in Fig. 1E). There are ongoing efforts to design a framework for how to develop therapies that *prevent* PD³⁸. A reliable and readily accessible biomarker of neuronal alpha-synuclein (n-asyn) pathology (any robust assay, e.g. SAA, for aggregated alpha-synuclein in biofluids or skin) would facilitate

such efforts. Clearly the most pertinent population to target in efforts to prevent PD are those in NSD stage 2, i.e. with evidence of n-asyn pathology combined with subtle clinical signs/symptoms without functional impairments. Thus, if these individuals who are in NSD stage 2 are also taken into consideration, the total population of people that could potentially benefit from treatments that target alpha-synuclein would go beyond the 2,000,000 who exhibit n-asyn pathology and are diagnosed with PD or DLB today, and would be around 3 million in the USA. Not only does the inclusion of NSD-ISS stage 2 imply that there is a much greater number of people who could be eligible to be treated than those who are presently diagnosed with PD and DLB, it also means that they could receive treatment earlier in the disease process. This is potentially important because it has been proposed that treatments targeting alpha-synuclein aggregation are more likely to be successful if given earlier in the pathogenic process³⁹, akin to what currently is suggested for amyloid immunotherapy in AD⁴⁰. This notion is based on the idea that counteracting Lewy pathology when it is less widespread, and before neurodegeneration has progressed too far, might lead to greater preservation of brain functions.

Alzheimer's disease

The estimates discussed above do not consider that other neurological diseases beyond PD and DLB also frequently exhibit alpha-synuclein aggregates. Thus, studies have reported around 20-45% of people with AD also being SAA positive^{34,41,42} (Fig. 1D), which is consistent with around 50% of AD cases exhibiting Lewy pathology at post-mortem autopsy^{43,44}. Importantly, in the Swedish BioFinder cohort living individuals aged 40-85 who showed *mild* cognitive impairment to moderate dementia also exhibited a positive SAA in CSF in 21% of cases⁴⁵. Notably, about half of them were only positive for SAA, indicative of a “pure NSD”, while the other half exhibited biomarker evidence for concomitant AD pathology (biofluid- or bioimaging-marker positive for beta-amyloid and tau aggregates). Those who were positive for the SAA test exhibited a more rapid and severe decline across all studied cognitive domains, particularly evident regarding visuospatial function⁴⁵. This suggests they might benefit from therapies targeting alpha-synuclein aggregates. So far there are no studies

defining if AD patients with an n-asyn positive test also have signs of dopaminergic system degeneration, or subtle motor deficits, which could be an additional cause for targeting alpha-synuclein aggregates in this patient group. Because alpha-synuclein aggregates in the brain often appear later in the disease journey for most AD patients, it is unclear precisely what proportion of those currently diagnosed with AD in the USA currently are SAA positive. Considering both the aforementioned post-mortem autopsy findings in advanced AD and the BioFINDER biomarker data in mild cognitive impairment to moderate dementia, a reasonable estimate is that around 30% (i.e. 2,000,000) of the estimated 6,000,000 people affected by AD will display significant alpha-synuclein aggregates in the brain (Fig. 1D). Taken together, this means that in total the sum of the people with PD, DLB, prodromal synucleinopathy (subtle signs or symptoms, i.e. NSD stage 2) or AD with alpha-synuclein aggregates can be as high as 5,000,000 (Fig. 2).

Asymptomatic people with alpha-synuclein aggregates

An "elephant in the room" is that an estimated 8-12% of brains of neurologically *unimpaired* people exhibit alpha-synuclein aggregates at the time of death, i.e. incidental Lewy body disease ^{46,47}. Notably, people with incidental Lewy bodies at death have fewer surviving dopamine neurons in the substantia nigra ^{46, 47} and reduced catecholaminergic innervation of the heart ⁴⁶, suggesting that they are already on a path towards NSD-associated neurodegeneration. However, at the time of death, individuals classified as incidental Lewy body disease have not displayed any symptoms or significant functional deficits. Exactly when during the life of these individuals these Lewy bodies develop is not known. Therefore, it is unclear how many people in the USA at any given time have Lewy pathology in the brain and future cross-sectional epidemiological studies using n-asyn tests across different age groups is needed to provide further insight. Notably, a recent study in the Swedish BioFinder cohort of 1130 cognitively normal individuals aged 40-85 years showed that 8% of them were SAA positive in the CSF, indicative of significant accumulation of Lewy bodies ⁴² and exactly consistent with the prevalence of incidental Lewy bodies on postmortem neuropathological examination. If we imagine that in the future a n-asyn test would be

included as part of a health screening protocol in people aged 50 and above, will it be possible to develop markers to identify those that are highly likely to develop neurological symptoms? If everyone with a positive SAA was to receive treatment to reduce the risk of PD, DLB or Lewy pathology in AD, we would likely be treating at least 4-5 SAA-positive people destined to live their lives without symptoms for each person that would be expected to one day develop symptoms of neurodegeneration. This emphasizes the great importance of identifying and developing robust biomarkers (e.g. in biofluids or using brain imaging or digital outcomes with wearable devices) that indicate the start of the earliest signs of neurodegeneration, going beyond the initial presence of neuronal alpha-synuclein pathology. With such biomarkers it would be possible to start treatments in only those who are very likely to progress to neurological symptoms, unless treated with drugs that slow the progressive nature of the pathological changes. The concept of treating large numbers of people at risk for cardiovascular disease in order to prevent a relatively small number of myocardial infarcts or strokes has been discussed extensively ⁴⁸. This discussion now needs to be held for neurodegenerative diseases. It highlights the essential and urgent need to develop an SAA test, or another biomarker of n-asyn pathology in readily accessible tissues (as discussed above). This could permit large-scale population screening, and a future where secondary prevention is more imminent than just a few years ago.

Concluding remarks

In conclusion, the development and validation of the SAA test as a biomarker for Lewy pathology in the brain opens up many new opportunities in terms of more accurate and earlier diagnosis of the classical neuronal synucleinopathies PD and DLB, even before there are significant symptoms. Identifying the presence of alpha-synuclein aggregates before the clinical onset of major neurodegenerative changes is attractive because intuitively it should increase the chances of seeing benefits from therapies targeting alpha-synuclein. Furthermore, the SAA test provides us with a tool to help identify AD patients who not only exhibit the classical amyloid and tau pathologies but also display alpha-synuclein aggregates. Considering that anti-amyloid immunotherapies are currently being approved for the treatment of AD, it will be particularly important to

identify those patients who have Lewy bodies as a co-pathology since such alpha-synuclein aggregates are associated with more rapid and severe cognitive decline. The SAA test allows us to realize that the numbers of people affected by Lewy pathology is very large, probably in the order of 5 million with symptoms or minor signs in the USA alone, with an additional 10-15 million having alpha-synuclein aggregates but not (yet?) exhibiting any impairments of brain functions (Fig. 2).

While the SAA test is an important advance, it also presents us with significant challenges and sets research priorities. First and foremost, development of assays to detect abnormal neuronal alpha-synuclein (n-asyn) using peripheral tissue or fluids (as discussed above), and in a quantitative fashion, will be essential to enable wide population screening and risk stratification. Considering that only a minority of those who develop Lewy pathology are destined to significant symptoms and deficits during their lives, who should be offered such a test and would a population-wide screening ever be ethically and financially justified, and if so at what age? We also need to understand if there are situations (e.g. following infections, toxin exposure or brain trauma) when a person might temporarily exhibit n-asyn, but then later will test negative weeks or months after the initial insult. Finally, the ultimate and urgent challenge is to develop therapies that successfully target the downstream effects of pathogenic alpha-synuclein aggregates and slow progression of symptoms of NSD, or even postpone or prevent the emergence of symptoms in the first place. Our analysis highlights the fact that such a therapy focused on alpha-synuclein might be relevant to a several-fold larger population than only those given the clinical diagnosis of PD today. This should incentivize the research area and drug development even further to pursue aggregated alpha-synuclein as a therapeutic target. Importantly, only when such therapies are clinically validated will we realize the full value of the important SAA or other new assays to detect pathological alpha-synuclein in neurodegenerative disease.

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Conflicts of interest

PB declares employment for F Hoffmann-La Roche and stock ownership for F Hoffmann-La Roche, Acousort AB, Axial Therapeutics, Enterin Inc and RYNE Bio. TS declares consultancies for 4D Pharma, Acadia, AcureX, AskBio, Amneal, Blue Rock Therapeutics, Caraway, Critical Path for Parkinson's Consortium, Denali, The Michael J Fox Foundation, Neuroderm, Roche, Sanofi, Sinopia, Sunovion, Takeda, UCB, Vanqua Bio, and Voyager. UK declares consultancies for Amprin, NurrOn, UCB, The Michael J Fox Foundation, American Parkinson Disease Foundation, and NIH. MB declares employment for UCB and stock ownership for UCB. KM declares support to his institution (Institute for Neurodegenerative Disorders) from The Michael J Fox Foundation. KM also declares consultancies for Invicro, The Michael J Fox Foundation, Roche, Calico, Coave, Neuron23, Orbimed, Biohaven, Anofi, Koneksa, Merck, Lilly, Inhibikase, Neuramedy, IRLabs, and Prothena. GP declares employment for F Hoffmann-La Roche and stock ownership for F Hoffmann-La Roche, Atea, Novartis, and Eli Lilly.

Table 1**The stages of the Neuronal Synuclein Disease Integrated Staging System (NSD-ISS)**

Stage	S - Neuronal α-synuclein biomarker	D - Dopamine dysfunction biomarker	Clinical signs and symptoms*	Functional impairment**
1A	+	-	-	-
1B	+	+	-	-
2A	+	-	+	-
2B	+	+	+	-
3	+	+	+++	+
4	+	+	+++	++
5	+	+	+++	+++
6	+	+	+++	++++

*People in Stage 2 show subtle clinical signs or symptoms that can be motor or non-motor: hyposmia, RBD, cognitive impairment, constipation, dysautonomia, depression, and anxiety. Those in Stages 3-6 exhibit motor and non-motor signs and symptoms associated with functional impairment. **The degree of functional impairment define stage 3 (slight), 4 (mild), 5 (moderate) and 6 (severe).

Figure legends

Fig. 1

- A. Schematic illustrating current estimates of the prevalence of Parkinson's disease (PD) and Dementia with Lewy bodies (DLB) in the USA. Each circle represents one million people. For references, see the main text.
- B. Schematic illustrating current estimates of how many people diagnosed with either PD or DLB in the USA are alpha-synuclein seed amplification assay (SAA) positive (red color) and therefore will fit the biologic definition of Neuronal Synuclein Disease (NSD). Each silhouette represents 10,000 people.
- C. Schematic illustrating an estimate of the number of people in the USA with signs or symptoms of prodromal PD or DLB who are SAA positive (red). Each silhouette represents 10,000 people.
- D. Schematic illustrating an estimate of the number of people in the USA with Alzheimer's disease (AD) who are SAA positive, ranging from low (red) to high (pink) estimates based on the literature. For references, see the main text. Each silhouette represents 10,000 people.

Fig. 2

Schematic illustrating an estimate of the prevalence of NSD in the USA today. Each circle represents one million people. Yellow circles are asymptomatic people, while the pink and red circles represent people with either motor or cognitive symptoms, as detailed in the key. For references, see the main text.

Figures

Fig 1A

Patients with PD or DLB in the USA today

332 million population (each circle = 1M)

Current clinical diagnosis of PD (1M) ●
Current clinical diagnosis of DLB (1.4M) ●

Fig 1B

Patients with PD or DLB in the USA today expected to be NSD+

Fig 1C

Most people with clinical signs /subtle symptoms of prodromal PD / DLB in the USA are expected to be NSD+

Assumption: prodromal signs (NSD stage 2) are present 5-15 years (equivalent to 25-75%) of the symptomatic phase of PD/DLB, equivalent to approximately 1M individuals in the USA

Prodromal signs

1M
>95% SAA+

Fig 1D

Patients with AD in the USA today expected to be NSD+

6M AD patients
21-45% SAA+ = 1.26-2.70M

Red = Low estimate SAA+
Pink = High estimate SAA+
Grey = SAA-

Fig 2

An estimate of the prevalence of people and patients with NSD in the USA

Around 18M (13M asymptomatic)

332 million population (each circle = 1M)

8% of those >40 yrs (around half of the USA population) are SAA+ without symptoms = 13M

Around 1M are prodromal, ie SAA+ in NSD stage 2, with signs and mild symptoms

2.02M pure NSD (PD + DLB)

1.26-2.70M (estimates vary) NSD + AD

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